

REHABILITATION OF CHILDREN WITH COCHLEAR IMPLANTS IN UZBEKISTAN

Z.I. Islambekova

Senior Lecturer, Tashkent State Medical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20523070>

Abstract. *This article examines the practical aspects of rehabilitation for children with cochlear implants in the context of Uzbekistan. It emphasizes that the effectiveness of cochlear implantation depends not only on the success of the surgical procedure but also on the quality of subsequent auditory and speech rehabilitation. The main components of the rehabilitation process are described, including audiological programming, development of auditory perception, speech and language therapy, psychological and pedagogical support, as well as the role of the family. The importance of early intervention as a key factor in speech and communication development is highlighted. The article concludes that a comprehensive and practice-oriented approach is necessary to ensure effective rehabilitation and social integration of children with hearing impairments.*

Keywords: *cochlear implantation, rehabilitation, children with hearing impairment, auditory and speech development, early intervention, surdopedagogy, inclusive education, Uzbekistan.*

INTRODUCTION

Cochlear implantation has become one of the key areas of assistance for children with severe hearing impairments in Uzbekistan in recent years. The expansion of access to high-tech medical care, the introduction of early diagnostic programs, and increasing government attention to issues of disability and inclusion are creating the foundation for systemic changes in this field. At the same time, the surgical procedure for cochlear implantation itself is only the initial stage of a comprehensive process upon which the child's further development depends.

Practical experience shows that without consistent and long-term rehabilitation, children with cochlear implants do not achieve the expected level of speech and auditory development. This is due to the fact that the implant does not restore hearing in its natural form but instead requires the formation of new skills for perceiving sounds and speech. In this regard, the organization of an effective rehabilitation system that includes medical support, pedagogical correction, and active family participation becomes especially important.

For Uzbekistan, this issue is of particular relevance. The number of cochlear implantation surgeries performed in the country is gradually increasing, including among young children.

An additional factor is the level of parental awareness. Practical recommendations on organizing an auditory-speech environment at home directly influence the effectiveness of the rehabilitation process and help fully realize the potential of cochlear implantation surgery.

Under modern conditions, a practice-oriented approach to rehabilitation becomes especially significant, taking into account the real capacities of the healthcare and education systems of Uzbekistan. Such an approach involves developing accessible support models for children, interdisciplinary interaction among specialists, and active family involvement in the corrective process.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The purpose of this article is to examine the characteristics of rehabilitation for children with cochlear implants in Uzbekistan, with an emphasis on practical aspects of organizing assistance. Particular attention is paid to existing problems, regional differences, and possible directions for improving the rehabilitation system.

Cochlear implantation is a modern high-tech method of medical assistance for children with severe sensorineural hearing loss and deafness, involving partial restoration of auditory perception through direct electrical stimulation of the auditory nerve. Unlike traditional hearing aids that amplify sound signals, a cochlear implant converts environmental sounds into electrical impulses and transmits them directly to the structures of the inner ear, bypassing damaged receptor cells.

RESULTS

The cochlear implant system includes external and internal components. The external part consists of a microphone, speech processor, and transmitter that capture, process, and transmit sound signals. The internal part, surgically implanted, includes a receiver and an electrode system inserted into the cochlea. This design allows the child to perceive sounds; however, this perception differs significantly from natural hearing and requires subsequent training.

The significance of cochlear implantation is especially great during childhood, when fundamental speech and cognitive functions are developing. Early surgery, usually performed before the age of three, creates conditions for more successful acquisition of oral speech, development of auditory attention, and integration into the educational environment. In some cases, children who undergo timely implantation and receive systematic rehabilitation achieve a level of speech development comparable to that of hearing peers.

In Uzbekistan, the introduction of cochlear implantation has become an important step in the development of the support system for children with hearing impairments. In recent years, the number of surgeries has increased, the material and technical base of medical institutions has expanded, and greater attention has been paid to the early detection of hearing disorders. These changes indicate the formation of a national support model for this category of children.

At the same time, it should be emphasized that cochlear implantation alone is not a complete solution to the problem. Receiving auditory sensations does not automatically lead to speech comprehension. In fact, the child learns to hear, distinguish, and interpret environmental sounds anew. Without purposeful surdopedagogical work, the development of полноценной communication remains difficult.

Practical experience demonstrates that the effectiveness of cochlear implantation depends not only on medical indicators but also on the quality of postoperative support. Regular adjustment of the speech processor, systematic sessions with a teacher of the deaf, and active family participation in the development of the child's auditory-speech skills all play an important role. Under conditions characteristic of Uzbekistan, the organization of accessible and continuous rehabilitation becomes a key factor in the successful integration of children with implants into society.

Thus, cochlear implantation represents not only a medical technology but also a comprehensive interdisciplinary system whose effectiveness directly depends on coordinated work among specialists of various profiles and family involvement. This determines the need for further consideration of the rehabilitation process as the main condition for realizing the potential of this technology.

Rehabilitation of children after cochlear implantation is a long-term, staged, and interdisciplinary process aimed at developing auditory perception, oral speech, and the child's integration into social and educational environments. Unlike children with normal hearing, a child with a cochlear implant does not immediately begin to understand speech after device activation. The child undergoes a gradual process of mastering sounds, starting from their detection to full semantic perception.

One of the key characteristics of rehabilitation is the necessity of early initiation. Systematic work is considered optimal immediately after activation of the speech processor. At this stage, the child's brain possesses high plasticity, allowing for the effective formation of new neural connections responsible for processing auditory information. Delays in beginning rehabilitation may significantly reduce final outcomes.

An important component is regular speech processor adjustment, the so-called mapping process. Stimulation parameters are selected individually according to the child's responses to sounds of different intensities and frequencies. During the first months after implantation, adjustments require more frequent correction because the child's auditory perception actively changes as experience accumulates.

Auditory-speech rehabilitation occupies a central place in the support system. It includes the sequential development of skills such as sound detection, discrimination, identification, and comprehension. The work is based on the principle of gradual complication of tasks and continuous reinforcement of auditory experience. In practice, this is implemented through special exercises, play-based methods, and the inclusion of auditory tasks in the child's daily activities.

Special importance is attached to the development of oral speech. Sessions with a teacher of the deaf develop correct pronunciation skills, expand vocabulary, and improve grammatical structures of speech. At the same time, it is important to consider that the pace of speech development may vary significantly depending on the child's age, individual characteristics, and upbringing conditions.

Another important feature is the necessity of active family participation in the rehabilitation process. Parents essentially become the main providers of the child's auditory-speech experience in everyday life. Their involvement determines the regularity of sessions, the quality of the speech environment, and the reinforcement of skills formed by specialists.

Rehabilitation also includes psychological and pedagogical support. Children may experience adaptation difficulties and behavioral characteristics associated with limited communicative experience at an early age. Specialists help develop interaction skills, attention, memory, and other cognitive functions necessary for successful learning.

A significant characteristic of the process is its duration. Rehabilitation is not limited to several months after surgery but continues for several years, especially during preschool and primary school periods. At the same time, continuity between various stages must be ensured, from early intervention to inclusion in the education system.

Thus, rehabilitation of children after cochlear implantation is a complex and multicomponent process whose effectiveness depends on early initiation, systematic implementation, an interdisciplinary approach, and active family participation. Consideration of these characteristics makes it possible to more fully realize the potential of cochlear implantation and create conditions for successful child development.

The rehabilitation system for children with cochlear implants in Uzbekistan is currently at the stage of intensive formation and gradual development. In recent years, significant steps have

been taken to expand access to high-tech medical care and improve conditions for the social integration of children with hearing impairments. At the same time, the structure of rehabilitation assistance is not yet fully integrated and is characterized by several organizational features.

A key role in the system is played by specialized medical institutions where hearing disorders are diagnosed, cochlear implantation surgeries are performed, and primary postoperative support is provided. These institutions are responsible for activating the speech processor and conducting the initial stages of adjustment. Major cities concentrate the main resources, including qualified specialists and technical equipment.

After the surgical stage, the child requires long-term auditory-speech rehabilitation carried out in various formats. In Uzbekistan, such assistance is provided both in state and private centers. These institutions employ teachers of the deaf and psychologists. The quality of corrective work directly depends on professional competence and experience.

The system of special education is also an important part of the rehabilitation process. The country has specialized educational institutions for children with hearing impairments where adapted educational programs are implemented. At the same time, inclusive education practices are developing, allowing children with cochlear implants to study in mainstream schools with appropriate support.

Family participation plays a significant role in the system. Educational programs for parents are of fundamental importance, and a unified system of counseling and support at all stages of rehabilitation is developing.

In recent years, positive trends have been observed related to the introduction of early hearing disorder detection programs for newborns, the development of regulatory frameworks in the fields of social protection and education, and the expansion of international cooperation. These processes create prerequisites for improving the rehabilitation system and increasing its accessibility.

DISCUSSION

A promising direction is the development of an interdisciplinary approach involving cooperation among medical specialists, educators, and psychologists. The implementation of remote support formats also becomes increasingly relevant, making it possible to provide consultative and methodological assistance to families living in remote regions.

Thus, the rehabilitation system for children with cochlear implants in Uzbekistan is characterized by a combination of positive dynamics. Further development requires comprehensive solutions aimed at increasing service accessibility, training specialists, and creating sustainable mechanisms for supporting children and their families at all stages of the rehabilitation process.

Particular importance is attached to the orientation toward practice-based assistance models adapted to the real conditions of the country's healthcare and education systems. This includes developing accessible support forms, strengthening personnel training, and creating sustainable mechanisms for interaction among medical, pedagogical, and social structures.

CONCLUSION

Thus, further development of the rehabilitation system for children with cochlear implants in Uzbekistan should be aimed not only at expanding high-tech medical assistance but also at ensuring its comprehensive support. Only under conditions of an integrated approach is it possible to achieve the main goal — the formation of полноценной communication, successful education, and integration into society.

REFERENCES

1. Koroleva I.V. Cochlear Implantation in Children: Rehabilitation and Speech Development. — Saint Petersburg: Rech, 2020.
2. Leongard E.I. Development of Auditory Perception in Children with Hearing Impairments. — Moscow: Prosveshchenie, 2018.
3. Mastjukova E.M. Correctional and Pedagogical Assistance to Children with Disabilities. — Moscow: Vldos, 2019.
4. Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan Materials on the Development of the System of Early Detection of Hearing Disorders in Children. — Tashkent, 2023.
5. Modern Approaches to Auditory-Speech Rehabilitation of Children after Cochlear Implantation // Defectology. — 2021. — No. 4. — pp. 15–22.
6. UNESCO Education for Inclusion: Global Perspectives. — Paris: UNESCO, 2021.
7. UNICEF Inclusive Education for Children with Disabilities. — New York: UNICEF, 2022.
8. World Health Organization Childhood Hearing Loss: Strategies for Prevention and Care. — Geneva: WHO, 2016.
9. World Health Organization World Report on Hearing. — Geneva: WHO, 2021.
10. Zykov S.A. Fundamentals of Surdopedagogy. — Moscow: Akademiya, 2017.